

TWINNING FOR NEW GRAPHENE-BASED COMPOSITES IN
ELECTROMAGNETIC INTERFERENCE SHIELDING

GrInShield, funded by EU, N° 101079151, HORIZON-CSA\HORIZON-AG

Standard Operating Procedures for the GrInShield project

Shielding efficiency measurements

Document contributors:

Contributor:	Institution:	Role:
Sebbache Mohamed	CNRS	Author
Duska Kleut	VINCA	Author
Kamel Haddadi	CNRS	Reviewer
Svetlana Jovanovic	VINCA	Reviewer

Document history:

Version:	Date:	Comment:
1.1 – Draft	21.10.2025.	D. Kleut first draft
1.2. V1	22.10.2025.	S. Jovanovic reviewed
1.2 – V2	22.10.2025.	K. Haddadi reviewed
1.3.-V3	30.10.2025.	M. Sebbache submitted the comments

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17483114

Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
CC-BY 4.0	Creative Commons License
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
VINCA	Vinca Institute of Nuclear Sciences, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade
FTPO	Faculty of Polymer Technology, Slovenj Gradec
IEMN – CNRS –UL	The Institute of Electronics, Microelectronics and Nanotechnology, National Centre for Scientific Research, University of Lille
Uni Oldenburg	Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg
WP	Work Package
WS	Workshop
GA	Grant Agreement
PM	Person Month
SS	Summer School
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures

Table of Contents

1. Description of document content and purpose	5
2. Introduction	5
3. Setup	5
3.1. Coaxial setup	5
3.2. Waveguide setup.....	6
4. Procedure.....	6
5. Analysis	7
6. References	7

1. Description of document content and purpose

The Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) have been prepared by GrInShield partners. This document aims to gather the most important data necessary for conducting reliable, reproducible, and accurate measurements of the material's various physical and chemical properties. This document outlines procedures for measuring the shielding efficiency of different materials in thin film form, using two different setups, including a vector network analyzer.

SOPs are written for the following devices:

- Coaxial system thin film shielding efficiency measurement
- Waveguide system thin material shielding efficiency measurement.

2. Introduction

Measuring the shielding efficiency of thin films involves using a vector network analyzer (VNA) with specialized fixtures to measure insertion loss (which represents the shielding effectiveness) in a specific frequency range. For different or higher frequencies, alternative test methods like a dual-chamber box for near-field measurements or a portable stand with horn antennas may be used, and results are often analyzed based on reflection and absorption losses. Using a VNA is a common method that uses a coaxial sample holder to measure the shielding effectiveness (SE) of planar materials by measuring insertion loss in a specific frequency range.

3. Setup

3.1. Coaxial setup

- Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) with appropriate frequency range - P 9374A Keysight Streamline USB Vector Network Analyzer, up to 20 GHz
- Coaxial test fixture (SMA connectors, sample holder)- custom-made at IEMN
- Calibration kit (SOLT standards) - TOSLKF50A
- Thin film samples (cut to standard dimensions)
- RF cables and adapters
- Computer with VNA control software

3.2. Waveguide setup

- Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) with appropriate frequency range - P9370a Keysight Streamline USB Vector Network Analyzer, 300kHz -4.5GHz
- Waveguide to coaxial adapters WR340 or other
- Calibration kit - 85561A
- Shielding material samples (cut into appropriate dimensions)
- RF cables and adapters
- Computer with VNA control software

4. Procedure

- Input RF power = -15 dBm
- IFBW = 100 Hz
- No of points = 801
- Perform full 2-port calibration at the measurement plane.
- Save all S-parameters in S2p format (txt)
- Verification steps
 - Empty structure (ports connected)

- Isolated ports

From empty isolated ports measurement, S_{21} in amplitude will be used to de-embed cable losses (be careful, to de-embed at low frequency, stand-off (distance separation must be kept identical to sample thickness))

From isolated ports measurement, S_{11} in amplitude will be used to de-embed cable losses 3/ nb of samples

- Put markers and add data to the Table.
- Record baseline (empty fixture) and reference (e.g., copper foil) measurements
 - Measure Aluminum (1 and 2 layers, 10 μ m/sheet, up to 4 sheets if requested)
 - Measure cellulose paper (1 and 2 layers, thickness: 100 μ m/sheet, up to 4 sheets if requested)
- Measure sample thickness before any RF measurement
- To prove repeatability: do 2 measurements on each sample; if they are not identical, the measurement will not continue. Repeatability must be identical.

5. Analysis

- Record all measurement parameters, sample details, and environmental conditions.
- Include calibration logs and raw S-parameter data.
- Summarize results in tabular and graphical formats.
- Calculate shielding effectiveness (SE) using: $SE = -20 \log_{10} |S_{21}|$
- Optionally separate reflection and absorption components.
- Plot SE vs frequency.
- Compare with reference materials and standards.

6. References

1. Siva Kumar, O. V. P. R.; Sundaramoorthy, A.; Padmapriya, V. S.; Raman D. N. Preparation of freestanding films from SWCNT/PANI nanocomposites using different blending techniques and characterization of their EMI shielding effectiveness in X-band, Phosphorus, Sulfur, and Silicon and the Related Elements, 2022, 197(3), 209-217, DOI: 10.1080/10426507.2021.2012680
2. Amaro, A.; Suarez, A.; Torres, J.; Martinez, P.A.; Herraiz, R.; Alcarria, A.; Benedito, A.; Ruiz, R.; Galvez, P.; Penades, A. Shielding Effectiveness Measurement Method for Planar Nanomaterial Samples Based on CNT Materials up to 18 GHz. Magnetochemistry 2023, 9, 114. <https://doi.org/10.3390/magnetochemistry9050114>